

Intelligent Mission Adaptive Controller (IMAC)

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ABSTRACT: Intelligent Mission Adaptive Controller (IMAC) is an exploratory research program that is investigating Distributed Artificial Intelligent (DAI) and Adaptive Neural System (ANS) technologies for application in active Electronic Countermeasure (ECM) resource management. The threat environment for tactical and strategic aircraft requires the ECM system to handle numerous, fast reacting, sometimes agile systems which vary in function from acquisition to weapons guidance. The ECM system must be capable of producing several jamming signals which may require the same transmitter resources or may interfere with each other (or other resources aboard the aircraft). Additionally, resources may be limited by either quantity or available power. Planning and optimization become important concepts to the aircraft facing a mission in such a dense environment. Additionally, the threat environment can become unpredictable forcing the planning and optimization processes to be refined on-board the aircraft. Since the human resources aboard most of these aircraft are overwhelmed with current avionics systems, machine processing must be developed to assist or handle the planning and optimization of ECM resources. IMAC is an attempt to capture and demonstrate the important concepts of an ECM resource manager. IMAC deals with the trade-offs between ECM effectiveness, system costs, and near and far term survivability. Technologies such as DAI and ANS enable IMAC to balance the trade-offs, adapt to change, and handle ambiguities. The work completed under the IMAC program is an initial requirements definition and some preliminary design involving the critical technologies. The paper to be presented will discuss the technologies of ANS and DAI and their application to resource management. Some of the critical problems the IMAC team has encountered will be discussed along with suggested designs.

1. INTRODUCTION.

The Intelligent Mission Adaptive Controller (IMAC) project is a joint in-house research program between the System Avionics and Electronic Warfare Divisions of the Air Force Avionics Laboratory established in Spring, 1987. Its overall goal is to provide a fusion of system integration and advanced artificial intelligence (AI) expertise from the System Avionics Division with the electronic warfare system and application expertise from the Electronic Warfare Division. The general problem chosen was the exploratory development of an intelligent ECM resource management system for a next-generation fighter aircraft. This system must be capable of real-time adaptation to the dynamics of the threat environment based on pre-flight optimal planning for the specific mission and projected threat. In order to accomplish this capability, we needed to develop both a real-time ECM processor for the aircraft and a ground based planning and optimization system. This problem provides a platform for both investigating fundamental problems in AI applications research and advanced support technology of interest to the System Avionics Division.

2.0 BACKGROUND.

The operational objective of the IMAC program is to enhance mission survivability for a next-generation fighter by reducing aircrew workload and providing adaptation and planning technologies to the avionics and avionics-support facility.

2.1 PILOT OVERLOAD.

The threat environment of the post 2000 era is expected to be dense, less predictable/recognizable, and faster reacting. Aircraft in such an environment must react quickly to multiple threats on the basis of environmental data characterized by noise, deception, uncertainty, mode changes and novelty. Additionally, each threat may require a coordinated response in two or more spectral bands. With the complexity of the threat response decisions and the required reaction time, the air crew will most certainly be overloaded especially when considering the needs of the other avionics and weapon delivery systems. Introduction of a sophisticated mission planning system will reduce air crew workload during the mission at the cost of a heavy pre-mission workload. The expertise of the aircrew in planning against and adapting to the threat must be supplemented by more intelligent mission planning and avionics resource management systems. Integrated EW and advanced processing techniques provide a means for reducing the load of the air crew in both cases and providing a more rapid and effective response. However, the complexity of the decision processing exceeds the capability of traditional software/processing techniques.

2.2 DESIGN ISSUES.

Two critical functions needed to supplement the aircrew decision process are planning and adaptation. These are exactly the two capabilities where people excel and computers fail.

2.2.1 PLANNING.

Traditional approaches to the countermeasure selection problem use sensor information and look-up tables to prioritize threats. Then a second look-up table provides a list of countermeasure techniques for selection against the threat. Initially, it appears that a clever expert system may provide better countermeasure selection by offering heuristic rules which sort and select the knowledge needed to make selections. Certainly automatic tree pruning methods will help the "look-up" scheme. Many AI techniques increase the capability (and maybe the speed) of a resource manager, but the most efficient real-time management comes from planning schemes.

A simple example shows the potential of a good planning system. The following shows how a first-come first serve selection strategy may be inadequate:

An aircraft's flight plan crosses through 3 threat envelopes: SAM (surface to air missile) 1, SAM 2, and SAM 3 (see figure 1). Countermeasure techniques A, B, and C are used to reduce the effectiveness of the SAMs (see table 1). Each technique, however, can be implemented to counter only one threat at a time due to constraints such as implementation resources, spatial configurations, or timing constraints. If the aircraft selects techniques as it

confronts the threats (a first come, first-serve selection with no planning), technique A is chosen to counter SAM 1, technique B is chosen for SAM 2, but for SAM 3 no technique is available for use.

FIG 1: Flight Path

A planning scheme allows the system to "look ahead" to the confrontations that will occur during the mission. Using the same example a simple planning scheme of pre-prioritizing the threats is used:

The flight plan is examined to prioritize the threats based on the threat's effectiveness against the aircraft (see table 2). Techniques are chosen for confrontation based upon this priority planning. SAM 3 is the most effective threat, hence technique A is chosen first to counter SAM 3. SAM 1 is second in priority, but since technique A is unavailable, technique B is chosen. Finally, technique C is assigned to SAM 2, the lowest priority threat.

TECHNIQUE SELECTION TABLE

	1st Choice	2nd Choice
SAM 1	techn A	techn B
SAM 2	techn C	techn B
SAM 3	techn A	techn C

TABLE 1: Technique Table

The priority method handles the threats in an order that will provide an increase in the countermeasure system performance because high priority threats will be handled first. If the priorities of the threats follow the order of confrontation the technique selection will be the same as in the first-come, first serve method in this case. The important point is that you are guaranteed to handle the most lethal threat(s).

A third selection method (probabilistic planning) combines the threat priority with a countermeasure effectiveness and optimizes system performance by analyzing all options. The following example illustrates this:

THREAT EFFECTIVENESS TABLE

Threat	Effectiveness
SAM 1	50%
SAM 2	40%
SAM 3	60%

TABLE 2: Threat Effectiveness Table

A table showing the effectiveness of the techniques against the threats (table 3) is used along with the threat effectiveness table (table 2) to create a table which displays confrontation effectiveness of the threats when the penetrating aircraft uses the suggested countermeasure techniques (table 4). Equation 1 shows how the threat effectiveness percentages for table 4 are arrived at using tables 2 and 3:

$$\text{EQUATION 1: } E_T^{\text{confrontation}} = E_T * (1 - E_{\text{tech vs T}})$$

where E_T is the effectiveness of the threat. $E_{\text{tech vs T}}$ must be subtracted from 1 in order to translate to a threat effectiveness. The resulting percentage, $E_T^{\text{confrontation}}$, relates the effectiveness of the threat given the situation where the countermeasure is applied.

TECHNIQUE VS. THREAT EFFECTIVENESS

	Techn A	Techn B	Techn C
SAM 1	85%	60%	*
SAM 2	*	40%	80%
SAM 3	70%	*	50%

* Technique not used against threat.

TABLE 3: Technique Effectiveness Against Threats

In the example given, the confrontation percentages given in table 4 are used to calculate total mission effectiveness percentages. Note that from the point of view of the penetrating aircraft, it is desirable to have low threat effectiveness. Since the effectiveness of the threats are relatively high without use of countermeasures, the following calculations will only show the two situations where all threats have been countered:

In situation 1, technique A is applied to SAM 3, technique C is applied to SAM 2, and technique B is applied to SAM 1. In situation 2, technique C is applied to SAM 3, technique B is applied to SAM 2, and technique A is applied to SAM 1. The total mission threat effectiveness percentages are calculated as follows:

EQUATION 2:

$$E_T^{\text{Total (scenario)}} = E_{T1}^{\text{confrontation (SAM 1)}} + E_{T2}^{\text{confrontation (SAM 2)}} (1 - E_{T1}^{\text{confrontation}}) + E_{T3}^{\text{cnfr (SAM 3)}} (1 - E_{T1}^{\text{cnfr}} - E_{T2}^{\text{cnfr}} (1 - E_{T1}^{\text{cnfr}}))$$

$$E_T^{\text{Total: situation 1}} = 39.9\%$$

$$E_T^{\text{Total: situation 2}} = 50.8\%$$

The probabilistic approach guarantees the best result given the data used. However, it does so at the cost of extensive processing. Even a simple but realistic case could overwhelm the computational resources in the aircraft, if not the ground support facility, because of the combinatorial explosion of options it must analyze. A successful planning system must be a compromise between the two extremes of the guaranteed optimal but expensive results of the probabilistic method, and the fast and inexpensive results of the first-come first-serve method. The sub-optimal but cheaper prioritization method gives a result better than first-come first-serve without the processing complexity of the probabilistic method.

SCENARIO EFFECTIVENESS TABLE

	1st Choice	2nd Choice
SAM 1	Techn A 7.5%	Techn B 20%
SAM 2	Techn C 8%	Techn B 24%
SAM 3	Techn A 18%	Techn C 30%

TABLE 4: Scenario Threat Effectiveness (Using Countermeasures)

2.2.2 ADAPTATION.

Adaptation is fundamental to the survivability of an aircraft. In its most basic sense, adaptation means the ability to alter a system response when the environment changes in such a way that its effectiveness is maintained. The changes in the threat environment which require adaptation are i) the introduction of novel threats or ii) changes in the operating modes for known threats. Some of these changes can be anticipated and planned for. But even with the extensive threat intelligence and analysis which the intelligence community provides the Air Force, there will be surprises. Novel threats and threat mode changes will be encountered. Thus adaptation is required.

Currently two general approaches to making an aircraft adaptive to the threat environment are available. First, the avionics system covers a wider range of threats or threat modes than what has been actually encountered. For example, an emitter identification table may allow parameter X a range of A to D for a threat system even though that parameter has only been observed between B and C in anticipation of a wartime change in that parameter:

$$X: A \leftarrow B \leftarrow \text{-----} \rightarrow C \rightarrow D$$

Second, an avionics reprogramming support system modifies the avionics software on the ground to cope successfully with threat changes beyond the adaptive ability of on-board avionics system. An example of this would be a case in which parameter X is found outside the range A - D. To handle this, the parameter range for X is extended to include it:

$$X: A \leftarrow B \leftarrow \text{-----} \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow E$$

Both approaches are necessary. No on-board avionics will be perfectly adaptive to the threat. Further, the threat change must be verified to prevent susceptibility to threat manipulation and deception. Adaptation must therefore be tempered by fusion of data from multiple sources with the expertise of threat analysts.

The two components of this integrated adaptive avionics and avionics-support system will play two fundamentally different roles. The on-board will be more reactive or "fire fighting": it must realize that there is a problem and make a quick and safe adaptation to maintain survival. The ground support system can provide an adaptation based on a more careful, long term analysis which considers a much wider range of options. Both approaches must be integrated so that the adaptive avionics can be reprogrammed when changes beyond its programmed range are encountered, and the ground system's assumptions can be checked based on post-mission analysis of the adaptive avionics system performance.

3.0 FUNCTIONAL SYSTEM DESIGN

The key characteristics of the IMAC problem discussed above dictate an integrated avionics and avionics-support system design approach. An effective system must 1) provide ground-based support for the optimization of ECM techniques for pre-planned flight routes and tactics, and adaptation to threat changes beyond the adaptability of the on-board system, 2) provide an embedded airborne EW system that implements the ground-based system's ECM plans and offers real-time, adaptive responses upon encountering unexpected, "pop-up" threats, 3) integrate the two functions. There will always be a limit to the amount of information and computational power available to an on-board system. Optimization and adaptation of the aircraft threat response beyond that limit must be accomplished on the ground. Further, operational considerations require a separation of ground and on-board optimization and planning. The aircrew will require the ability to control the aircraft's response or at least the range of that response. Also, as mentioned before, vulnerability of an adaptive avionics to deception by the threat will be prevented by limiting the on-board adaptation. Finally, the response times required in combat can only be satisfied if the avionics has the ability to anticipate threats and to use pre-planned fallback responses. Controlling the on-board adaptation and providing pre-planned responses require use of a complementary ground support system.

3.1 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is any technology which emulates the capabilities of human intelligence. These capabilities include perception, understanding, problem solving, planning, and learning. Any technology which captures these capabilities is AI under this definition. This approach to AI allows us to be open to whatever specific technologies will solve the ECM planning problem. In our evaluation of AI technologies we have distinguished two broad categories of AI. The first applies techniques of formal and informal logic such as expert systems, logic programming, and heuristic search. The second relies on models of natural intelligence such as artificial neural systems (ANNS), simulated evolution systems, and society of minds systems. This is not a sharp division--hybrid systems which fuse technologies from each

category are possible. However, these are two distinguishable general approaches which have different properties. These differing properties suggest a mixed system architecture using one or the other approach as appropriate. The expert systems approach is fundamentally an application of logic and thus provides a deterministic response with the correctness of the result guaranteed if the assumptions encoded in the rules are correct. For this reason, an expert system architecture for the on-board ECM response system was explored (see section 3.6). The properties of ANSs, on the other hand, lend themselves to the fuzzy decision making needed in the ground based mission planning system.

3.2 AI DESIGN CONCEPTS.

A description of the general, functional capabilities required by IMAC is given in Figure 2. These capabilities are also a good summary of the key concepts in AI: Representation, Perception, Novelty Detection, Internal Model, Response, Reasoning, Adaptation, Attention, Learning, Training, and Knowledge Acquisition. The requirements for IMAC are for nothing less than an intelligent system = one capable of assessing and understanding its environment, planning an appropriate response, and learning from its experience. Our research into appropriate technologies for this system has therefore focused on artificial intelligence technologies.

Figure 2

3.2.1 MEMORY

The core of IMAC is its memory - its internal representation or model of the environment it has to deal with and its own resources, goals, plans, etc. Without such a capability in some form, there will no basis for anticipating a threat and system resource needs, for realizing that an unexpected event has occurred, or for evaluating the effectiveness of its responses. The threat inner model is continuously updated by the avionics sensor system.

3.2.2 PERCEPTION

Two crucial functions provided by the perceptual system are Feature Analysis and Novelty Detection. The amount of information handled by IMAC will easily overwhelm it unless it is reduced to the features relevant to generating the correct threat response: e.g. radar A is tracking me, site B will probably launch an IR missile. Novelty detection is needed to identify pop-up threats and flag them for special consideration.

3.2.3 RESPONSE

The response subsystem starts with a situation assessment performed off of the inner model. The key decision is whether the tactical threat situation is familiar or novel: a pop-up threat or an anticipated threat in an unanticipated mode. If the situation is judged to be as anticipated - familiar - the pre-planned response is executed reflexively by the response resource controller. This is analogous to a pain reflex where a fast response is needed and there is no uncertainty as to what to do.

Reasoning is required in a novel situation where the reflexive responses may be ineffective or even dangerous. To meet the short response times, it may be necessary that the reasoning be based on pre-planned fallback responses or reserve response resources. A critical issue for this reasoning is that a response be found which counters the threat with minimal disruption to the mission plan stored in IMAC's memory. If extensive alteration of the plan is allowed, the risk will be that IMAC will become disoriented and will have to fall back to a purely reactive, reflexive mode (or a "first-come, first-serve" selection). Whatever response is arrived at in the reasoning must be consistent with the goals and constraints incorporated in the original mission plan. For example, an emphasis on low observability in the mission may preclude consideration of an active countermeasure. Thus IMAC must in some sense be a goal-seeking system.

3.2.4 NOVELTY DETECTION

A crucial ingredient for learning from experience is knowing when the environment has changed. The Novelty Detection and Novelty Memory in IMAC address this problem. If a novel pop-up threat is encountered, the novel situation along with the chosen response and a temporal snapshot of the threat environment is recorded by a Novelty Recorder for later analysis. The system will thus bring back for the learning system what novel events occurred, their context, and its response. If this information is sent as a burst during critical situations, it would then serve as the system's dying scream to warn others of the danger. What is to be learned by the system, or by others if it doesn't survive the encounter, is how to handle this new threat.

3.2.5 ADAPTATION

The on-board adaptation subsystem will operate in conjunction with the response subsystem. The actions produced by the response function give rise to predictions in the tactical evaluation module that the threat situation will change as planned: track broken, missile misses, etc. The Tactical Evaluation compares that prediction with reality (as projected in the inner model by the Info Request) to assess how well the response function is performing. That evaluation leads to the crucial function in any learning system: credit assignment. The evaluation must result in a diagnosis as to why the system is or is not performing as expected. In particular, credit must be assigned to the specific steps or steps in the reasoning process responsible for the system's evaluated performance. This credit assignment will in turn result in appropriate reinforcement of that step - performed by the Reinforcement subsystem - by increasing its probability if successful (reward) and decreasing its probability if not (punishment). As the system gathers experience, various fallback responses will receive more or less reinforcement and correspondingly receive more or less consideration. Also, with experience the inner threat model can be updated by Model Update with information as to which responses did or did not work as predicted. Failure of a response to produce the anticipated result may require Info Requests to the sensor system for more information concerning the situation.

3.2.6 LEARNING/TRAINING/KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION

The purpose of the Learning system is to assimilate all the unexpected events experienced by the system or communicated to it by other systems and decide what should be done. These learned responses will be reprogrammed into the IMAC system by Training. Knowledge Acquisition will be the means by which the knowledge in the system will be initially acquired. This will be either by explicit instruction or by watching. The idea behind the second possibility is that the most efficient way for the aircrew to plan their mission is to pre-fly the mission (with speed up modes as appropriate) and choose responses with the advice of the ground based mission planning system. The system "watches" this by storing the situation/responses chosen by the instructor. Altogether, this support capability allows the IMAC system to be updated with new instructions and newly learned responses.

3.3 ARTIFICIAL NEURAL SYSTEMS.

ANS systems have properties which are important for electronic warfare applications. Especially important to us are the parallelism, dynamic information processing, adaptability, and noise tolerance of ANNs. An Artificial Neural System is a massively parallel network of weighted links joining nodes whose values were summations of the weighted input signals passing through the links passed through a sigmoid function (Figure 5). Information processing in an ANS network is in the dynamics of the network as the nodes interact with each other. Those dynamics are controlled by the links and associated weights between nodes. When given new input signals, the network dynamics will drive to a steady state which represents the desired solution.

A possible design strategy for the IMAC ground system is to design an ANS network which stores enough knowledge of ECM resource management to drive the network dynamics to an optimal or good solution for whatever ECM problem is presented to the network. Mechanisms will be then added so that the network can monitor its own performance and modify its dynamics so that its processing adapts to the dynamics of the threat environment. This threat environment would be the ground support system's inner model updated with the latest threat information received from aircraft recorders and communication links.

3.4 PLANNING AND OPTIMIZATION

The planning to be accomplished in the ground support system is a problem in optimization at every instant and over time. The resources to be used are of two different types. The jamming power to be managed represents a renewable resource since the same amount of power is available at each instant. The problem is to optimize the use of the jamming power in the sense of maximizing estimated effectiveness of the complete jamming response against the complete threat situation. Trade-offs will be between different techniques against specific threats or a combination of threats. Non-renewable resources for the ECM system are expendables such as chaff, flares and decoys. They are nonrenewable in the sense that once used they cannot be recovered as a resource. The problem here will be when to use the expendable against some threat situation during the course of the complete mission so as to maximize survivability over the entire mission. Trade-offs will be between using an expendable now versus later against an anticipated threat. This necessitates a representation within the system of the mission and the expected threat environment: an inner model of the entire mission. The jamming power management can acquire some of this

temporality if it is assumed that once committed, a jamming technique is never dropped until it is complete (e.g. track is successfully broken). The idea is that dropping a technique after it has begun results in an unacceptable vulnerability to the targeted threat. In such a case, the jamming resource being used will not be available until the technique is successful. Thus the complete ECM threat response optimization will be a spatio-temporal optimization over the complete mission against the expected threat environment laid out in the ground support system threat simulation. The overall problem is to optimize with the competing goals of survivability and mission success, and the constraints of renewable, renewable-after-time, and non-renewable resources.

3.5 KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION.

Knowledge acquisition is critical to any AI system whether it be an expert system or ANS. Any AI system is only as good as the knowledge acquired and stored in the system. Our research into knowledge acquisition went through four phases. In each case we were attempting to find the threat response decision rules for IMAC. In Phase I, we used a commercial knowledge acquisition tool called "First Class". This tool and others like it will derive a decision tree from examples supplied by the domain expert. The procedure will be to (i) ask the expert to give a list of factors and possible values for those factors he uses in his decision making and (ii) for a representative sampling of situations defined by those factors and their values give the recommended actions. From this information, the tool computes the decision tree which best captures the given situations and actions. The problem we found with this method was that it did not adequately capture the complex interrelationships amongst threats and techniques.

In Phase II, we investigated the Fuzzy Cognitive Map (FCM) methodology of Dr Bart Kosko (USC). Questionnaires were developed which gave the concept nodes for a network representation of the rules. Experts were asked to supply the appropriate connections and weights. A connection between concepts A and B represents the rule: If A, then B. The corresponding connection matrix was hand coded and processed for evaluation. The FCM was better for capturing interrelationships than a decision tree. However the FCM questionnaire was difficult to use and could not easily represent correlations. All too often the expert objected to simply connecting one node to another node -- he wanted to represent multiple concepts as joint influence on a given concept.

In Phase III we developed with Mr Pat Simpson at Verac (now at General Dynamics) software which automated the production of a connection matrix for the concepts and provided a much more user friendly questionnaire. However, it was still difficult to capture correlations. In addition, we had not adequately focused our knowledge acquisition on the key concepts and interrelationships needed to adequately characterize the ECM problem.

Finally, in Phase IV we developed a spreadsheet questionnaire which focused on key threat characteristics (Threat ID, Type, Mode, Range, Probability of Detection of Kill), technique characteristics (Technique ID, Type, Effectiveness, Cost) and correlations (changes in effectiveness when used in conjunction with another specific technique). Our use of a spreadsheet and focus on basic features of the threat situation resulted in a much more successful knowledge acquisition effort for a network capable of planning threat prioritization and response taking into account correlations between threat features and interrelationships between techniques.

3.6 AIRBORNE SYSTEM.

As mentioned earlier, current EW systems evaluate sensor information, classify the threats, and implement look-up tables to find the best ECM response. This approach limits the ECM response to the constraints of the look-up table's optimization scheme where, usually, very little information is considered for response generation. In other words, the system will never offer a better response than is listed in the look-up table.

In order to use available ECM resources more effectively, it is important to consider all available information. Present algorithms, look-up tables, and other conventional techniques are unable to fully optimize responses; therefore, new techniques must be implemented to accomplish the goal of resource optimization.

One possibility for the optimization of ECM responses is the application of expert systems. Expert systems offer several advantages for the optimization process which include 1) a generic inference engine which implements many specialized rule-based systems, 2) rapid system development - only rules governing the optimization of techniques need to be developed, 3) rapid system reconfiguration - only a few rules generally have to change to implement reconfiguration or modification, and 4) an ECM response which has been optimized by any number of selectable parameters.

Figure 3

An expert system also offers such advantages as audit trails, the ability to trace the flow of logic used in the inferring process, and the ability to limit search space. The audit trail capability aids in the verification and validation processes of system development and modification, therefore, reducing the system support and development costs. Careful structuring of the rule-base also facilitates the limitation of search space which results in smaller inference cycles, thus, saving valuable CPU and response time. The advantages of expert systems over normal processing techniques warrant a closer look at the implementation of an expert system into an EW system.

The importance of expert system design cannot be overstressed. Expert systems offer many advantages to software engineering but they also have drawbacks. For example, small rule bases, let's say 25 rules, will fire or infer quite rapidly; however, add 25 more rules and the system may take 5 to 10 times longer to infer. So you can see that system design is very important to overall system effectiveness. The top-level functional design of the airborne EW system could appear as Fig 3. The following is a brief description of each of the functional subsystems:

1) Mission Knowledge Base - this is the output of the ground-based system. This knowledge base contains the location of each anticipated threat and the anticipated ECM response needed for each threat.

2) Sensor Information - for the purpose of this airborne system, all sensor information has been assumed preprocessed with the threat having been tagged with an identification, or tagged as unidentified, with appropriate range, azimuth, and mode information.

3) Position and Threat Identifier - this subsystem accepts inputs from the sensors and then searches the Mission Knowledge Base for the time-based and location-based comparisons of detected threats and expected threats.

4) Assertion Generator - this subsystem generates the appropriate assertions needed for the inferring of the System Rule-Bases and stores them in the Assertion Buffer. It also updates the ECM Resource Monitor.

5) Assertion Buffer - stores assertions for detected threats to expedite the inferring process in novel situations.

6) Inference Engine - processes the assertions in the Assertion Buffer through the appropriate System Rule-Base.

7) Situation Evaluator - a rule-base which makes a quick decision on the overall urgency of the present environment and novel threat and then triggers the appropriate System Rule-Base.

8) System Rule-bases - various rule-bases for the inferring of specific situations such as quick reactive responses, completely optimized responses, etc.

a) Reactive Rule-Set - provides rapid response to novel situations but doesn't always provide optimal responses.

b) Optimized Rule-Set - provide optimal response to novel situations but requires more time than the reactive rule-set.

c) Mission Knowledge Base Update Rule-Set - updates the Mission Knowledge Base when novel situations cause conflict with planned ECM techniques.

9) ECM Resource Monitor - this subsystem chiefly lists all available ECM resources such as power, jammers, and expandables, and maintains a record of what is currently in use and what is available for use.

10) System Response - this subsystem interfaces with the actual system components which implement the prescribed ECM techniques.

As mentioned earlier, expert systems can require a significant amount of time to infer; therefore, the system must be designed with this limitation in mind. In a real-time airborne EW system the inference time may be prohibitive if aircraft survival is important - which is usually the case. Given this, more inventive methodologies for expert system implementation must be considered. In the system described above an AI ground-based system is used to produce a Mission Knowledge Base. The ground-based system takes all available mission data and ELINT information and creates identity and location data for the ECM optimization rule base. Once the rule base has been fired, appropriate optimized ECM techniques are generated and recorded in the Mission Knowledge Base for use in the airborne EW system.

Since most of the time-intensive planning and optimization has been completed, it is now possible to complete a real-time response to unexpected, pop-up threats in the airborne system where fractions of a second may be the difference between mission success and loss of aircraft and crew. The key to this system is planning.

Now that the Mission Knowledge Base is complete, it can be loaded on-board the aircraft via embedded computer resources. Once the aircraft is airborne the EW system begins to monitor the sensor information and data bus traffic

through the Position and Threat Identifier. Basically, at this point, there are two possible modes of operation 1) Normal Operation - no unexpected threats are detected, and 2) Novel Operation - an unexpected threat has been detected.

During Normal Operation, the Position and Threat Identifier monitors the Sensor Information for threat identification, modes, and threat positional information and monitors the data bus traffic for aircraft positional information. At this point the Position and Threat Identifier simply compares information. If a threat is detected, for example an SA-6 with range r, azimuth a, and mode m, the Position and Threat Identifier would then acquire the aircraft's position and calculate the threat's approximate position. The Position and Threat Identifier would then search the Mission Knowledge Base for a threat at that approximate location or of that type. Assuming that there is a threat listed at that location, a comparison would be made of the identification. If the comparison was successful, the corresponding ECM technique would then be extracted from the Mission Knowledge Base since the system expected that threat.

The Position and Threat Identifier would then pass the ECM technique and pertinent threat information to the Assertion Generator which would create the corresponding assertions for storage into the Assertion Buffer. The ECM technique would then be implemented through the System Response subsystem. As you can see, as long as the threats that are encountered match the threats in the Mission Knowledge Base, the AI system never has to complete an inference cycle. Up to this point, the system is very efficient and responses are optimized.

The other mode of operation is the novel mode where an unexpected threat is encountered. Operation of the Position and Threat Identifier is much the same except this time it found no match in the Mission Knowledge Base. At this point it passes the novel threat information, such as positional, identification, and mode information to the Assertion Generator which creates the necessary assertions for firing the Rule-Based Systems. These assertions are then inserted into the Assertions Buffer for use by the Inference Engine.

In order to describe the operation of the system, an example will be used. Suppose up to this point we are presently in the range of an SA-x and an SA-z, both of which were expected threats. For these threats we knew what to do and are presently applying the appropriate ECM techniques. We now encounter an SA-y which is unexpected (not in the Mission Knowledge Base). The proper assertions have been created and are now in the Assertion Buffer. At this point, we know the priorities and techniques being used for the SA-x and SA-z; so, we must prioritize the SA-y and optimize the techniques being used. In order to do this, we must start the Inference Engine.

The first set of rules to be fired is for the Situation Evaluator. This rule-set determines the urgency of the present situation. For our example, assume the SA-y is in search mode and poses no real threat for the present. The Situation Evaluator would then select the appropriate rule-set, the Optimized rule-set for this case. This indicates that the situation is not extremely urgent; and, the system can take into account more parameters for the best possible response. The system then would recommend a technique to counter the threat given the present environment. This technique would then be passed to the System Response Subsystem.

The Inference Engine would then query the ECM Resource Monitor to verify the effect of the new technique on future, planned techniques (those in the Mission

Knowledge Base). If there was a conflict, for example your next expected threat cannot use the recommended technique in the Mission Knowledge Base because of the pop-up threat, it is desirable to update the Mission Knowledge Base. This is a time-intensive process, therefore, requiring monitoring by the Situation Evaluator. The Situation Evaluator will determine the urgency of the situation and determine if there is enough time to process the request. If it is determined that there is enough time, the Mission Knowledge Base Update Rule-set will be fired resulting in an updated Mission Knowledge Base. The total inference time, however, is negligible when compared to the ground-based system since only minor modification of the knowledge base is necessary.

Now assume that the SA-y had been discovered in track mode. The system would have responded the same way up the point of the Situation Evaluator. The System Evaluator, let's assume, determined that this threat required a more urgent response. In this case, the reactive rule-set would have been fired and a technique generated that may not be fully optimized. This is where the trade-off takes place. Sometimes you must trade optimization for speed and vice-versa. This is why you need multiple rule-sets. For this system only two levels of optimization are described but many levels could be implemented.

The use of the system in this way allows the user to determine by rule-sets what type of response is preferred in given situations. This system design offers the best of all worlds - 1) Pre-Planned ECM Resource Management for proposed flight routes, 2) Optimized and reactive techniques for unexpected threats, and 3) Inflight Mission Pre-Planning when unexpected threat ECM techniques conflict with pre-planned techniques.

One issue not covered yet is deviation from pre-planned flight routes. This of course, destroys the advantages of pre-planning; however, the system is able to handle the situation. When this occurs, the pilot or crew member should be able to signal that deviation from the flight plan has occurred. At this point the Position and Threat Identifier quits searching the Mission Knowledge Base and proceeds directly to the Assertion Generator. System response is then as described in the Novel Operation description. System response would be expected to provide reactive responses in dense threat environments and optimized responses in limited threat environments. In this case, the system produces responses no worse and generally better than today's systems.

Figure 4

3.7 GROUND SUPPORT SYSTEM

The two purposes of the IMAC ground support system (see Figure 4) are to (i) assist the mission planners in finding the optimal plan for the mission given the latest threat information, and (ii) aid in post-mission analysis. Finding the optimal plan or re-optimizing a plan with new information is an extremely expensive task in time and computational resources. In addition, the reasoning involved requires a great deal of fuzzy trade-off decisions. We thus chose to investigate an ANS approach because of its inherent parallelism and its ability to implement fuzzy reasoning.

3.7.1 ANS APPROACH

The dynamic knowledge processing capability combined with the parallel processing ability of ANSs suggests use of an ANS architecture for the mission planning function of the ground support system. The most difficult part of formulating an optimal mission plan will be consideration of multiple competing/cooperating goals and constraints, making the resulting complex trade-offs, and searching through the immense number of possibilities. An ANS can accomplish the trade-offs between competing/cooperating goals and constraints by negative (= competing) and positive (=cooperating) links between nodes representing the possible goals, constraints and responses. Approaches which provide a mathematical basis for the performance of such a network have been developed by Cohen & Grossberg at Boston University and Hopfield at California Poly-Tech. Even in a ground support facility, parallel processing will be required to consider the immense number of possibilities in time for the next mission. ANSs provide an approach to implementing this requirement.

Figure 5

If we represent the network energy as a function of its node values, then the network processing can be interpreted as a descent down the network energy surface to a stable state at the bottom of one of the "energy wells". A combination of proper knowledge encoding and noise in the input signals will help prevent settling into a non-optimal energy well. The key to proper design of such a network is therefore in careful choice of weights and linkages between nodes. The knowledge (long term memory) of the network is represented in those weights. Thus, the network's dynamics are controlled by its stored knowledge and it is that stored knowledge which will insure that it produces a correct solution.

An ANS network is literally a knowledge processing system and is only as good as the knowledge stored in it. Thus, the problem of knowledge acquisition for such a network is therefore critical. For an ANS, knowledge acquisition is through training with an adaptation algorithm. Adaptation of the network knowledge processing is through modification of its weights. The adaptation algorithm is typically some function of the values of the (supervised learning) nodes connected by the link (unsupervised learning) and possible some reinforcement or error signal. Thus prior established knowledge is hand coded into the network's weights and modified adaptively as new information comes in via the adaptation algorithm. A wide variety of adaptation algorithms are available for this and will be investigated in future phases of our research.

3.7.2 ANS EXPERIMENTS

A simple threat response decision net with six techniques against three threats was successfully implemented. The net was implemented as a feedforward, fixed weight net with standard sigmoid output functions tailored for optimum performance. The net settled to a state representing the most plausible decision for all possible cases of threat inputs.

An example of a network derived from the threat-techniques spreadsheet discussed in 3.5 is given in Figure 5. We assume for simplicity, two radar threats in track mode and four possible response techniques. The essentials of the situation are (i) Radar B is more dangerous than Radar A because of its greater Probability-of-Detection (PD), (ii) Techniques 1 and 3 are more effective against their corresponding threats than Techniques 2 and 4 respectively, (iii) Techniques 1 and 2, 2 and 3 enhance each other, (iv) Techniques 1 and 3, 1 and 4 interfere with each other. The net shown in Figure 5 encodes this information in an ANS representation form. The last stage of the net (the Cost node, Cost interconnections, and feedback) is designed to manage power usage. This final cost-stage was not tested.

Competitive nets were studied for their dynamics and stability in implementing a trade-off decision. Use of Grossberg's Shunting Equation was found to provide the required stability and to settle to a solution much more quickly than the net tested above.

Finally a modification of Kosko's Temporal Bi-Directional Associative Memory was designed to solve a temporal optimization problem. Tests of the design with the Traveling Salesman Problem have not been completed.

4.0 RESULTS.

Most work under IMAC has been in understanding and developing design concepts for the system. Preliminary results from this in-house research are as follows:

a) use of a spreadsheet format for acquiring threat/threat response information was found to be superior to decision tree and Fuzzy Cognitive Map formats. Capturing complex correlations was the key problem; a good knowledge representation scheme for complex correlations is essential. We still feel that more research is needed in knowledge representation and capture.

b) a preliminary version of the on-board threat response system as described in 3.6 was implemented in Goldworks on a Hummingboard AI coprocessor for an IBM AT clone.

c) a series of experiments as described in 3.7.2 was conducted to test design concepts for the ground mission planning system.

More detailed experiments in both the expert system based airborne system and the ANS based ground support system are planned.